

BKN681-9-33-3-21-3, KNth 361-1-8-6, BR51-245-1, BR51-331-4, BR52-90-2, Pusa 2-33, Tea-1-P₂-5-2, B-4-90-2, IR577-24-1-1-5, IR578-111-2-2, IR41154-357-2-3-2, IR1544-238-2-3,

IR1550-8, IR2053-362-1-4-4, IR2053-375-1-1-5, IR2060-213-2-17, IR2061-464-2-4-4-6, IR2061-522-6-9, IR2070-414-39, IR2070-423-2-5-6, IR2071-527-3-1-5, IR50, IR52, PR107,

BJ-1, FH663, CR44-1018, CR75-93, CR167-10, CR164-12, CR316-639, HAU5-9-1, HAU5-101-1, RP5-32, RP-291-74, UPR173-23, UPR82-1-7, and UPR173-1-8. *ℓ*

Reactions of IRRI rices to rice diseases in Tamil Nadu

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In 1984 thaladi (Sep-Oct to Jan-Feb), rice in Tamil Nadu was damaged by yellowing syndrome (YS), which often caused total crop loss, and by bacterial blight (BB), *Helminthosporium* (H), sheath blight (ShB), and grain discoloration (GID). The 1984 International Rice Yield Nursery was grown under this disease pressure, and rices were evaluated using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (see table).

Of 30 entries in the trial, 10 had multiple disease resistance: BR40-300-1-2, IR18349-22-1-2-1-1, IR19672-140-2-3-2-2, IR21820-154-3-2-2-3, IR21848-65-3-2-2, IR25587-133-3-2-2-2, IR25603-20-2-1-3-2, IR27325-63-2-2, IR28118-138-2-3, and IR31917-31-3-2. IR28118-138-2-3 had the best resistance and yielded 4.4 t/ha. IR18349-22-1-2-1-1, IR21820-154-3-2-2-3, and IR25587-133-3-2-2-2 combined high yield (5.3 t/ha) and disease resistance. *ℓ*

Reaction of IRYN rices to some important diseases in Tamil Nadu, India. ^a

	YS	H	BB	ShB	GID
BG379-2	0	3	3	5	5
BR153-2B-10-1-3	0	7	5	3	5
BR40-300-2-1	3	3	3	3	3
BW295-4	5	3	5	5	5
BR-IRGA-409	3	7	3	7	7
IR18349-22-1-2-1-1	0	3	1	3	3
IR19672-140-2-3-2-2	0	3	3	3	5
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	1	3	3	1	3
IR21848-65-3-2-2	0	3	3	3	3
IR22082-41-2	0	7	3	3	3
IR24637-38-2-2-1	0	5	5	3	5
IR25587-133-3-2-2-2	0	3	3	3	3
IR25603-20-2-1-3-2	0	1	3	3	3
IR25604-99-1-3-2-2	0	5	3	3	1
IR27316-96-3-2-2	0	5	5	3	1
IR27325-63-2-2	0	3	1	3	3
IR28118-138-2-3	0	3	1	1	3
IR28150-84-3-3-2	0	5	5	1	5
IR329723-143-3-2-1	0	3	5	5	5
IR31917-31-3-2	0	3	3	3	3
IR4744-295-2-3	0	5	5	3	3
RAU2004-669-2-13 (BIET2004)	3	7	5	7	3
RNR74229	5	5	7	7	5
RNR74802	0	5	5	3	3
RTN16-2-1-1-1	0	5	3	3	5
SI-PI 692106	3	7	5	7	7
UPR254-85-1-TCA 3	5	5	5	5	3
X.3-D.T.	5	3	3	5	5
IR42	3	5	3	5	5
Co 43 (local check)	5	3	1	3	3

^aScored by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 1-9 scale: 1 = resistant, 9 = susceptible.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

INSECT RESISTANCE

Resistance of *Nephotettix virescens* gene sources to Asian *N. virescens* populations

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Tungro virus, vectored by green leafhopper (GLH) *N. virescens*, is a major problem where GLH-susceptible varieties are grown. IRRI and national program greenhouse screening has identified more than 1,300 cultivars with GLH resistance. Seven genes for *N. virescens* resistance have been identified in genetic analysis at IRRI and the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, and

some of those genes have been incorporated into improved rice varieties. Although these varieties have been effective in controlling GLH, there is evidence that the levels of resistance conveyed by the different genes vary with location. We sought to determine the levels of resistance conveyed by the seven genes to local GLH populations in the Philippines (IRRI), India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, and Vietnam.

Resistance was determined in seedbox screening and nymphal survival tests. In